

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Safari****FIRST NAME: Jean Paul****PROGRAM CODE : DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied uses US or UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used MS Word 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Conducting a successful research is a daunting task. What should a researcher check (*should – doability*) before undertaking a study on a given topic?**
 - The researcher should pick a topic which is widely researched. As such, there will be no serious challenges to access literature review and some secondary data that can just be transformed to allow the paper to meet academic requirements.
 - The researcher should check whether the target audience may find the work worth an effort, whether it has a policy significance, whether it helps with his/her personal and professional goals, and whether it is not likely to harm the researcher and or participants if findings are honestly reported.¹**

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 7.

- The researcher will ask whether there are students and scholars undertaking the same study so that they can collaborate. As such, it will be easy to use some of their findings.
 - The researcher shall ask whether there is enough funding from local NGOs and the government ministries. Otherwise, the study is not worth pursuing.
2. **Every researcher contemplates various types of questions throughout their research efforts. Which of the following statements best describes those questions?**
- The researcher asks philosophical questions to engage in endless research. After all, research is a lifelong endeavor. Research has existed since the times of Plato and continues to take place. Every finding can be challenged.
 - Researchers ask both general but concrete questions. Without these, the study would be useless. In fact, every research is assessed based on the availability of the opportunity to investigate these questions.
 - Researchers ask conceptual questions so that they get the meaning of key terms. They pose practical questions to detail how they will go to the field and ask applied questions to discuss how research participants will be encouraged to participate in the study.
 - They ask conceptual questions to improve the understanding, ask practical questions to get an explanation of what should be done after an improved understanding, ask applied questions to check what must be understood before attempting to solve a social challenge.²**
3. **While every research builds on extant studies, researchers are warned against plagiarism. To avoid this, sources from extant work should be**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15–18.

cited. Which of the following statements best describes plagiarism and reasons for avoiding it?

- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information and gives credit to the author of that source of information. It should be avoided because it violates ethics; it fails to credit the others' great work; it is an academic offense and should not be exaggerated. One of ways to minimize it is citing sources, paraphrasing and indicating sources. As such, the writer can prove to the audience that the writer read extensively so that they do not doubt his / her education credentials.
- We talk of plagiarism when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. It should be avoided because it violates ethics; it fails to credit the others' great work; it is an academic offense and should be avoided at all costs.³ Citing is one of techniques used to avoid plagiarism. In addition, it is an opportunity to assure readers about the accuracy of facts, share with them the research tradition that informs the work being undertaken, and help readers want to follow or extend the same area of inquiry.⁴**
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information and does not mind giving credit to the author of that source of information. It should not be avoided because it does not seriously violate ethics; it is not an academic offense. It cannot be avoided. Without the use of secondary data, researchers may not be able to motivate the proposed study, provide an opportunity to explore competing views, may inspire the researcher on existing models and how these can be adopted for their own research and analysis.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information and does not mind giving credit to the author of that source of information. It should not be avoided because it does not seriously violate ethics; it is not an academic offense. It can be maximized by using in-text citation,

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

⁴ Turabian, 86.

footnotes, paraphrasing and duly indicating sources of information. However, secondary sources can be boring.

4. **Before choosing the research approach for qualitative studies, researchers are advised to think about the nature of knowledge and how we know we know. Which of the following statements best makes that description?**

- Research must be free to describe their research topic and clearly outline the research questions and objectives. They must also discuss their methodology. While ontology, epistemology and axiology are important, they are not necessarily interrelated.
- Researchers must address ontological considerations because this tells about what knowledge is; address epistemological considerations because this defines how we know what we know; consider axiological dimensions because these clarify what values go into knowing what we know; and methodological considerations to account for the process for knowledge creation. These are interrelated.⁵**
- Researchers must address ontological considerations because this tells much about the problem statement; address epistemological considerations because this outlines research objectives; consider axiological dimensions because these clarify ethical considerations; and methodological considerations to account for the process of ensuring rigor.
- Qualitative research seeks to generalize findings. Qualitative researchers. Researchers must address ontological considerations because this tells about what knowledge is; address epistemological considerations because this defines how we know what we know; consider axiological dimensions because these clarify what values go into knowing what we know; and methodological considerations to account for the process for knowledge creation.

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, 8.

5. **Qualitative studies employ various approaches. Which of the following statements is not the best description of the outlined qualitative approaches?**
- Social constructivism is one of the qualitative approaches. It is also referred to as interpretivism or naturalist inquiry. Scholars believe that knowledge emerges from the social and cultural environment of human beings.
 - Critical theory is one of qualitative research approaches. Scholars who espouse it are engaged in criticizing the works published by Antic Philosophers to show how modern epistemologies are better than Antic ones.⁶**
 - Pragmatism does not take any side. Scholars who use this believe that every approach can have its weaknesses and therefore recommend a combination of whatever approaches and methods that are best suited to answer to a research question.
 - Statement 1 and 3 are true, while statement 2 is false
6. **In qualitative research, there are many genres. Each one must meet trustworthy criteria. Which combination of statements below best describes these concepts (genres and trustworthiness)?**
- There are many genres in qualitative research including case study, ethnography, narrative inquiry, grounded theory and phenomenology. Researchers must do their best to ensure that research participants can trust in them before they can share their lived experiences. Without this, the researcher may not have access to protected sites.
 - Genres is borrowed from French to mean “gender.” It means that as a research student, one must trust their advisor based on the expertise, availability and accessibility as well as shared interest in the research agenda irrespective of their gender.
 - Phenomenology deals with lived experience; ethnography deals with cultural or social groups; grounded theory seeks to generate a**

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 7.

new theory; narrative inquiry deals with stories; case study deals with time and place.⁷ Whatever genre the researcher chooses, they must meet credibility, dependability, transferability and confirmability criteria. In a nutshell, researchers must be transparent enough about their own emotions, research process and how they arrived at presented conclusions.⁸

- Trustworthiness, among other things, provides details about dependability. This discusses how the PhD student was independent from his/her research mentor / advisor.

7. Data analysis involves coding approaches. Which of the following statements best describes this concept?

- Coding consists of sorting data into meaningful categories. It may be either open coding consists of putting data generated into categories, axial coding consists of using the categorized data to posit with a theoretical model, while selecting coding involves storytelling, whereby story is generated from links between data categories.⁹**
- Coding consists of analytic approaches. These involve quasi-statistical whereby recurring concepts are calculated to determine relative importance of terms and concepts; template approaches whereby codes are derived from theory or research question or from an initial read of the data serve and remain flexible as analysis goes on; editing approaches whereby codes are emergent; and immersion approaches, which is the least structured, most interpretive, emphasizing researcher insight, intuition.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 11.

⁸ Ibid., 11

⁹Ibid., 11

- Coding consists of identifying whether a question asked in descriptive, interpretative or theoretical. They are helpful in validating the research hypotheses.
 - Coding consists in establishing whether data collected are a good fit for either a confirmatory study or an exploratory one. As such, the data are likely to be numbers and stories, respectively.
8. **In qualitative research, authors must discuss limitations and delimitations. One of limitations may have to do with the quality of the study. However, triangulation can set off some limitations. Which of the following statements best describes the difference between delimitation and limitations as well as how triangulation helps set off the limitations?**
- In research, limitations and delimitations mean the same things. It depends on how the researcher clearly explains it. Triangulation, which consists of drawing triangles on the report's cover page, does not in any way have to do with limitations.
 - Limitations refer to the research scope while delimitations highlight the research weaknesses. Triangulation can help address both in the same manner.
 - Limitations clarify the research weaknesses while delimitations discuss the research scope¹⁰. Triangulation can use different methods such as documents review, survey, interviews, observations, whatever combination is appropriate, to offset some research limitations.¹¹**
 - The concepts “delimitations” and “limitations” are exact opposites as shown by the prefix “de.” They can be addressed by subjecting researchers to intense training in data cleaning.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 77–79.

¹¹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 195–97.

9. **Which of the following format is the best description of the Turabian Author-Date citation style in case of a single author?**
- Author's first name Author's last name. Edition. Title (underlined). Editor(s)/Translator(s). Place: Publication Press. Date.
 - Author's last name, Author's first name, "Title," Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press. Date.
 - Author's last name, Author's first name, Edition (if available). Date. *Title*. Editor(s)/Translator(s) (if available). Place: Publication Press.¹²**
 - Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title, Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press. Author's academic title such as Dr.
10. **The European Commission's English Style Guide seeks to harmonize style rules. Which of the following statements provides the best guide on adding *-able*?**
- When adding *-able*, authors and translators should consult bilingual dictionaries because not all European countries have English as their official language.
 - Based on the principle of equality enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1949, every country representative should use their mother tongue with the help of the interpreter.
 - The English Style Guide recommends the use of American English instead of British English because powerful countries in Europe are allies of the United States of America through NATO.
 - When adding *-able*, authors and translators should drop a final silent *-e* at the end of the stem (debate – debatable) so long as it does not change the pronunciation of the preceding consonant (as in**

¹² Turabian, 136.

changeable or traceable). In case of doubt, the Oxford English is helpful.¹³

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¹³ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2020), 17.